

DIAMAS Receives Grant to Develop Diamond Open Access Publishing in Europe

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

For immediate release

Aix-Marseille Université, cOAlition S, and Science Europe are pleased to announce that they are participating in a Horizon Europe project called '[Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication](#)' (DIAMAS). The 3-year project, launched on the 1st of September 2022, receives funding in the context of the Horizon Europe call on *Capacity-building for institutional open access publishing across Europe*.

The DIAMAS project, which was awarded a grant of €3m, brings together 23 European organisations that will map out the landscape of Diamond Open Access publishing in the European Research Area and develop common standards, guidelines and practices for the Diamond publishing sector. The project partners will also formulate recommendations for research institutions to coordinate sustainable support for Diamond publishing activities across Europe.

Moreover, the DIAMAS project will interact closely with the global community of the '[Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#)' signatories. While the project will spearhead some of the activities laid out in the Action Plan, it welcomes complementary actions and contributions. As a first step, DIAMAS project partners and members of the Diamond Open Access Plan Community had the chance to meet and discuss collaboration opportunities during the Diamond Open Access Conference (Zadar, Croatia, 19 - 20 September 2022).

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The 23 organisations participating in the DIAMAS project include Aix-Marseille Université (AMU) (Coordinator), OPERAS, CNRS, EIFL, the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV), Jisc, the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER), University of Barcelona, University of Zadar, University of Zagreb, Science Europe, the European University Association (EUA), the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA), Arctic University of Norway, the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), University of Göttingen, SPARC Europe, Utrecht University, the National Documentation Centre (EKT), IBL-PAN, the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), and the European Science Foundation (ESF) (acting for cOAlition S).

About Aix-Marseille Université (AMU)

Aix-Marseille Université (AMU) is a public research university with a history going back to the University of Provence, founded in 1409, and five main campuses situated in Aix-en-Provence and Marseille.

It is the largest university in the French-speaking world, with about 80,000 students and a budget of €750m. It is ranked as one of the top 5 universities in France.

About cOAlition S

Plan S is an initiative for open-access publishing launched in 2018 by cOAlition S, a consortium of 27 national research organisations and charitable foundations, including the European Commission and the WHO. From 2021, the plan requires all

scholarly publications on the results from research funded by cOAlition S organisations to be published in Open Access Journals, on Open Access Platforms, or made immediately available through Open Access Repositories without embargo.

About Science Europe

Science Europe is an association of major research funding organisations (RFOs) and research performing organisations (RPOs). It was established in October 2011 and is based in Brussels. The association facilitates co-operation among its

members and supports excellence in science and research in all disciplines, acting as a

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platform to develop positions on research policy issues and to address policy messages to European institutions, researchers, national governments, and the public.

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